

Unpacking MSME Compliance: Barriers in Food Safety Regulation

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ABSTRACT: MSMEs are a key pillar of Indonesia's economy, yet food safety compliance among MSME actors remains low despite an extensive regulatory framework. This study uses a normative juridical approach to examine barriers to MSME compliance with food safety regulations in Indonesia. Findings show that although a comprehensive and multi-layered regulatory framework exists across multiple institutions, implementation is hindered by limited food safety knowledge, inadequate infrastructure, financial constraints, and fragmented regulatory authority. These conditions create confusion and weaken compliance at the MSME level. The study concludes that regulatory complexity is a major obstacle to effective food safety governance. It recommends simplified Food Safety Quick Guidelines for MSMEs, supported by capacity building and government support, to improve compliance, strengthen public health protection, and enhance MSME competitiveness.

KEYWORDS: MSMEs, food safety, compliance, Indonesia, regulation

1. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are a cornerstone of Indonesia's economy. MSMEs contributed over 60% to the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employing nearly 97% of the workforce (Putri et al,2024). During economic crises, such as the 1998 monetary crisis and the 2008 global financial crisis, MSMEs even gave shown resilience (Susan,2020).

MSMEs often operate with traditional methods, due to limited technological integration and financial constraints (Gunapriya et al,2025). For example, in Indonesia, street vendors have become an integral part of people's lives, in both urban and rural areas. Street food is affordable, and fits the tastes of most people (Hermanu,2015). Unfortunately, sometimes in street vendors, food is handled unhygienically, allowing food to be contaminated with toxic microbes, as well as unauthorized food additives (Saputra,2012).

Many street food vendors produce food with harmful substances, namely formalin, borax, methanyl yellow, cyclamate, and rhodamine B as preservatives or colorants. A study in Semarang found that 78.3% of street food samples contained formalin (Anjani et al,2025). These chemicals pose danger to public health and can lead to severe health issues, especially in vulnerable people such as children and elderly (Anjani,2025). Consumption of food sold in street vendors has been linked to foodborne illnesses, namely typhoid and paratyphoid. A study carried out in Jakarta found that eating street food can increase the risk of paratyphoid fever by over three times compared to other food sources (Vollaard et al,2004).

MSMEs constitute an inseparable part of Indonesian society and play a significant role in supporting the national economy as well as the distribution of food products to the public. Given their extensive presence and accessibility, MSMEs have become one of the primary sources of food consumption for many communities in Indonesia. Consequently, the state bears the responsibility to ensure that food products produced and distributed by MSMEs comply with established food safety standards and do not pose risks to public health. This responsibility includes not only the formulation and enforcement of regulatory frameworks, but also the provision of supervision, guidance, and institutional support to enable MSMEs to meet food safety obligations effectively.

The Government of Indonesia has established several laws and regulations to address food safety issues involving MSMEs. These legislative instruments reflect the government's dual objective of ensuring food safety while simultaneously promoting the growth of small-scale businesses as a pillar of the national economy. The legal framework governing MSME food businesses is primarily rooted in *Food Act 18/2012*, which establishes the obligation of food business actors to guarantee the safety, quality, and nutritional value of food products distributed to the public. This framework is further complemented by Consumer Protection Act Number 8 of 1999, which emphasizes consumers' rights to safe products and accurate information. In addition, *Government*

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Regulation 1/2026 on Food Safety further strengthens Indonesia's food safety governance by emphasizing risk-based food safety control, inter-agency coordination, and the responsibilities of business actors in maintaining food safety standards throughout the production and distribution chain. In practice, food MSMEs are also subject to technical regulations issued by the National Agency for Drug and Food Control (NADFC/BPOM), including certification and supervision mechanisms for home-based food industries through the SPP-IRT licensing system. Furthermore, the implementation of *Halal Product Assurance Act 33/2014* has expanded regulatory obligations by requiring halal certification for food products circulating in Indonesia. Collectively, these regulations demonstrate that Indonesia's food governance system seeks not only to protect public health and consumer interests, but also to strengthen the legal capacity and competitiveness of MSMEs through a framework of supervision, standardization, and institutional support.

However, despite the existence of regulations governing food safety for MSMEs, food safety incidents arising from the consumption of food products processed and distributed by MSMEs continue to occur frequently in Indonesia. This condition indicates that the mere establishment of regulatory frameworks is insufficient to ensure effective compliance and consumer protection in practice.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative research design with a normative juridical approach to examine the limitations faced by Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) that contribute to low compliance with food safety regulations in Indonesia. The research is conducted through the analysis of relevant statutory and regulatory frameworks governing food safety, consumer protection, and MSME licensing, complemented by secondary sources such as academic literature, policy reports, and institutional publications. The study further identifies and critically examines structural and practical barriers to compliance, including technological constraints, financial limitations, and deficiencies in legal awareness among MSME actors. In addition, this research evaluates the role of government intervention, both in facilitating food production processes and in strengthening consumer education, as integral components in enhancing compliance with food safety standards.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses the key factors that hinder compliance with food safety regulations among Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Indonesia. Although a comprehensive regulatory framework governing food safety has been established, effective implementation at the level of business actors remains limited. Two interrelated factors are particularly significant in explaining this compliance gap, namely limited food safety knowledge and awareness among business actors, as well as insufficient understanding of food safety standards among MSMEs. These conditions reflect not only individual capacity constraints, but also broader structural issues such as inadequate access to training, limited dissemination of regulatory information, and uneven institutional support. Together, these factors contribute to suboptimal compliance practices, which in turn increase the risk of food safety violations and pose potential threats to public health.

3.1. Limited Food Safety Knowledge and Facilities Among Business Actors

Limited food safety knowledge and inadequate facilities remain significant barriers affecting compliance among MSME business actors in Indonesia. Many MSMEs operate with limited understanding of fundamental food safety principles, including hygiene standards, safe food handling practices, labeling obligations, and the proper use of food additives. This lack of knowledge is often compounded by insufficient access to training and limited dissemination of regulatory information, particularly for MSMEs located in rural or underdeveloped regions. In addition, many business actors face infrastructural and financial constraints that hinder their ability to provide adequate production facilities, sanitation systems, storage equipment, and quality control mechanisms necessary to comply with food safety standards. As a result, compliance is frequently perceived as burdensome and costly, leading to the continued circulation of food products that may not fully meet regulatory requirements.

A survey of drinking water in Yogyakarta in 2017 illustrates this issue. Although Yogyakarta is a relatively affluent urban centre on the island of Java, the study found that 89% of water sources and 67% of household drinking water were contaminated with faecal bacteria (UNICEF). This contamination is largely attributed to open defecation, a practice in which individuals dispose of human waste in open environments such as street gutters, behind bushes, or directly into bodies of water (Kashiwase, 2019). Notably, this makes Indonesia the third-largest country globally in terms of open defecation prevalence, after India and Nigeria.

The Role of Training and Subsidies in Strengthening MSME Compliance

The issue of limited food safety knowledge among MSMEs is also reflected in the approach adopted by NADFC in its training programs. Food registration has consistently been prioritized as a central topic in training sessions due to the government's objective of increasing the number of registered food products and businesses. In support of this objective, NADFC introduced an

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online food registration system (e-registration) as part of its regulatory modernization efforts. However, the implementation of this system continues to encounter technical and practical obstacles, particularly for MSMEs located in regions with limited technological infrastructure and inadequate human resources. These constraints contribute to the reluctance of many business actors to register their food products (Puri, 2023). Moreover, the level of understanding among business actors regarding food registration procedures has become one of the indicators used to assess NADFC's institutional performance, measured through the increase in product registrations. Nevertheless, an excessive focus on registration procedures alone may overlook other equally important aspects of food safety education. As demonstrated by recurring food safety violations, many food business actors still lack basic knowledge regarding prohibited food substances, including the use of formalin as a food additive. Accordingly, food safety training programs should not be limited to administrative compliance, but must also include broader and more practical educational materials tailored to the specific needs and capacities of MSMEs.

Government support also plays a crucial role in providing essential infrastructure to foster the growth and development of MSMEs (Unnevehr, 2000). This includes not only physical infrastructure such as roads, electricity, internet access, and transportation networks, but also institutional support like business licensing systems, financial services, and access to training facilities. When these basic structures are in place, MSMEs can operate more efficiently, reduce costs, and reach wider markets. In addition, governments can strengthen digital infrastructure to help MSMEs adapt to modern business environments, especially in areas such as e-commerce and digital payments. Supportive policies, tax incentives, and simplified regulations also help small businesses grow without being burdened by complex administrative processes.

Overall, strong government support creates an enabling environment where MSMEs can become more competitive, innovative, and sustainable contributors to the economy.

3.2. Insufficient Understanding of Food Safety Standards Among MSMEs

MSMEs often encounter difficulties in navigating complex regulatory frameworks, licensing requirements, and compliance obligations under both local and international food safety standards (Margaretha&Hendrawan, 2024). This issue remains one of the primary factors contributing to low compliance with food safety regulations in Indonesia. Many MSME actors possess limited knowledge regarding hygiene standards, food handling procedures, labeling requirements, and licensing obligations mandated under Indonesian food safety regulations. This may be caused by multiplicity in food safety legal framework in Indonesia. As of early 2020, there are approximately 88 regulations related to food safety that are enacted in several types of regulation, namely Acts, government regulations, ministerial regulations, and Head of NADFC regulations (Putri, 2022).

The multiplicity of Indonesia's food safety regulatory framework arises from the fact that food safety regulation falls under the authority of various ministries and governmental bodies according to their respective sectors. *Government Regulation Number 1/2026 on Food Safety* stipulates that the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries are responsible for regulating fresh food products, while NADFC is authorized to establish standards and requirements for processed food. In addition, the Ministry of Health is responsible for regulating ready-to-serve food, whereas local governments oversee food products produced by home-based industries. This fragmented allocation of regulatory authority has contributed to overlapping regulations, administrative complexity, and inconsistent implementation of food safety standards, particularly for MSMEs.

Multiple pieces of laws and regulations is more difficult to manage. In addition, the multiplicity of laws and regulations may create confusion among the public, particularly when overlapping provisions and regulatory inconsistencies arise between different governing authorities.

Food Safety Quick Guidelines for MSMEs

To address the persistent challenges faced by MSMEs in complying with Indonesia's fragmented food safety regulatory framework, it is recommended that the government establish simplified Food Safety Guidelines specifically tailored for MSMEs. Such guidelines would serve as a practical, consolidated reference that translates complex legal and regulatory provisions into clear, accessible, and operational steps. Rather than requiring MSMEs to navigate approximately 88 overlapping regulations issued by multiple authorities, the guidelines could harmonize key requirements on hygiene practices, food handling, packaging, labeling, and licensing into a single user-friendly document. This would help reduce regulatory confusion caused by the division of authority among institutions such as the Ministry of Agriculture, the Ministry of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, the Ministry of Health, NADFC, and local governments. In addition, the guidelines could be designed in a step-by-step format, incorporating visual aids, checklists, and minimum compliance standards to accommodate MSMEs with limited technical and legal knowledge. To ensure effectiveness, these guidelines should be widely disseminated through local government offices, digital platforms, and MSME assistance programs, and accompanied by capacity-building initiatives and training. By simplifying compliance requirements and improving regulatory clarity, such guidelines would enhance food safety practices, increase compliance rates, and ultimately strengthen consumer protection and the competitiveness of MSMEs in both domestic and international markets.

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4. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that although Indonesia has established a comprehensive legal and institutional framework governing food safety for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), effective compliance remains limited in practice. MSMEs continue to play a vital role in the national economy and food distribution system; however, their operations are frequently constrained by limited food safety knowledge, inadequate infrastructure, financial limitations, and low awareness of hygiene, labeling, and licensing requirements. These challenges are further reinforced by uneven dissemination of regulatory information and insufficient training and institutional support.

In addition, the fragmentation and multiplicity of Indonesia's food safety regulatory framework, distributed across various ministries and supported by approximately 88 overlapping regulations, create significant complexity for MSME actors. This regulatory dispersion results in inconsistent implementation, administrative burdens, and confusion regarding applicable standards. Consequently, despite the presence of robust laws such as the Food Act, Consumer Protection Law, and sectoral regulations issued by NADFC and other authorities, food safety incidents continue to occur, indicating a gap between formal regulation and practical compliance.

Therefore, this study concludes that improving MSME compliance requires not only enforcement of existing regulations, but also simplification and harmonization of regulatory guidance. The establishment of Food Safety Quick Guidelines for MSMEs is recommended as a practical policy instrument to translate complex legal requirements into accessible and actionable standards. Combined with capacity building programs and stronger government support, such measures are essential to improving compliance, protecting public health, and strengthening the sustainability and competitiveness of MSMEs in Indonesia.

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